

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361163823>

The Importance of Logical and Critical thinking in conservation of forests and ecology.

Conference Paper · October 2021

CITATIONS

0

READS

31

1 author:

Savio Saldanha

Loyola College

8 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

The Importance of Logical and Critical thinking in conservation of forests and ecology. [View project](#)

The Importance of Logical and Critical thinking in conservation of forests and ecology.

1) Abstract:

Conservation of forests and ecology is one of the pressing needs of human kind today. The topic is widely spoken about in academic circles, various local, national and international forums and also Pope Francis has stressed on the importance of caring for our common home, especially in his encyclical 'Laudato Si'. The Society of Jesus has adopted caring for our common home as one of its UAP's.

In this paper, I shall present how lack of long term planning, by the government and other agencies led to adverse effects on the ecology and the important role logic and philosophy can play in the conservation of forest and ecosystem. Being a student of Botanical science and having worked with MPSM in its various initiatives of ecological sustaining and enhancement projects, I have realized the importance and the far reaching effects of philosophical logic and critical thinking in conservation and reforestation initiatives.

2) Introduction:

In the late 80's and early 90's, the alarming decrease of forest cover and the noticeable change in the local climate prompted the government and the department of forest, Maharashtra to go for large scale afforestation program. The tree introduced for this program was teak (*Tectona grandis*). It was chosen due to its sturdy nature and the good quality wood which is in high demand for various purposes like making furniture and other articles. Various NGO's and civil groups also took up the initiative and actively supplied teak saplings to farmers and tribals. Vast swathes of land were brought under afforestation and reforestation programs. The result was the creation of huge areas of teak forests in the Western areas of Maharashtra. Everyone from the authorities to the people were elated by the success of this project and considered it to be a success. *Or was it?*

3) Ecology:

3.1) The Destruction- Prologue:

Even today, the urbanized population believes the over-romanticized stories of tribal-forest relationship. The tribal is closely united to the forest and both share a sort of symbiotic relationship. The forest provides the tribal with food, various herbs and roots for medicines and other uses; and also with wood for his various needs; the tribal in return protects the forest considering it as his deity. This might have been true at certain point of time. But the rapid spurt of population growth, and increased life expectancy due to penetration of medical services and better roadways connectivity to remote places, led to the tribal losing his connect to the forest. He could not resist the charm of rapidly spreading materialism and lucrative deals with pharmaceuticals and other corporate for various forest produce. This led to rapid depletion of forest cover, as more land was brought under cultivation to meet the demands of increased population. Several areas were left barren due to many factors like over-usage of fertilizers and pesticides. And hence when the problem came to fore, the bubble of symbiotic relation between humans and the forest was burst.

The problem began to manifest in several ways like increased soil erosion, leading to depletion of the nutritious top layer of soil, decrease in water level leading to increase in frequency of famines. The government and the various agencies working in these areas for the tribal upliftment felt the need to respond to this situation.

3.2) The So-called Solution:

It was decided to go for large scale afforestation and reforestation of areas particularly mountain slopes, to prevent soil erosion and other techniques like bunding were used to facilitate

water percolation. As mentioned earlier in this paper, the teak (*Tectona grandis*) was chosen for this purpose.

3.3) The Realization:

Once the chest thumping and back patting was done, it was observed that the teak forest was displaying strange behavior. A person visiting these forests was greeted with eerie silence, and barring few reptiles, and scavenger birds and animals, it was devoid of any birds, animals which should thrive in forests. It was now realized that the teak was not a traditional tree in these regions, it's introduction as a main tree had made it a dominant species, and it was suppressing other naturally occurring fauna, which was a source of food for insects and worms which were a sort of the bottom rung of the food chain, also the tree in itself was unfavorable for the birds to build nests, thus, the entire food chain had been affected. Also, the teak wood served only one purpose, making furniture and other items. The diversity which had traditionally existed in these areas for say, past 50-60 years was completely lost. This had caused severe damage to several forest herbs, roots, vegetables and medicinal plants and shrubs, many of which had become nearly extinct, or in some cases lost forever. To complicate the matter, the tribal youth did not know about the uses of these natural food and medicinal sources, and the only ones who knew about it were the elders who had not kept any written records. Also there was no record about the type of fauna which naturally occurred in these parts, with the forest department.

It was realized, albeit late, that a proper, methodical, rational study of the original vegetation should have been conducted before going for afforestation and reforestation drives. It had been a blunder to introduce teak on a large scale, without a prior study of its affects on the entire forest ecosystem.

3.4) Making Amends:

The study was now taken up with the searching of archives of the forest department, interviews with the elders in the villages and especially the medicine-men (vaidus) to get to know about the various types of trees and plants which were found in this region half a century ago. Also satellite imagery of the forest was requested from ISRO and was very helpful in getting the required information.

Accordingly it was discovered the types of dominant species of trees in this region were Blackcurrant, Tamarind etc. The saplings of these were procured and distributed to farmers and other stake holders, and a new initiative of reforestation was started. The new mindset being that if we can actually bring the ecosystem back to what it was, at-least in some parts with the same type of vegetation which used to grow naturally, then we can have a sustainable forestry, the diversity would also help the tribals to obtain the traditional non-timber forest produce, and create a forest based entrepreneurship development, with the tribal women in the lead. Thus began the NELFED Program of MPSM, Non-timber forest products: Enhancing Livelihood security for the tribal communities in Western Maharashtra through sustainable Forest-based Entrepreneurship Development.

4.1) The Role of Philosophy and logic:

As I was studying Philosophy and Logic, I felt that if the concerned agencies had applied the principles of logic to the problem, then the situation would have been entirely different. Let us try to look at the situation from the philosophical components:

- a) **Philosophical Problem:** In this case is deforestation. How can we improve the situation? What is the proper method to tackle the situation? To be precise we can take the recourse to Logic which is the science of methods of right reasoning, by valid inference and demonstration.

- b) **Philosophical Attitude:** The attitudes needed in this situation are to be:
- i. **Reflective-** thinking about the problem.
 - ii. **Willing to be guided by experience or reason-** Do we have any previous experience in this regards? Has anyone tackled such problem in our country or in other countries?
 - iii. **Speculative-** So, we have to go for afforestation and reforestation, do we have the facts and procedures in place of how to go on about it?
 - iv. **Uncertainty-** Ok, so the speculative solution offered is planting of teak, is it ok to go for a single species of tree to replace multi-species ecology? What can be the effect on ecosystem of the forest?
 - v. **Willingness to be objective/Persistence-** Can we take up the project on a pilot basis before going for mass intervention? If the first project fails what is the second option we have?
- c) **Philosophical Method:** Philosophical method consists of reflection or reflective thinking. Proper methodical observations should be carried out, hypothesis must be formulated and then it needs to be tested by further experiences. Thus, we see that proper method would have not allowed to go for planting of teak trees, because it was based on a mere hunch, that it would solve the deforestation issue. Rather reflective thinking would have cautioned against such a folly.
- d) **Philosophical Activity:** Comes with a feeling of challenge and the need to respond to such a challenge. It is not content with stopgap solutions or untested solutions rather takes into account the pondering, reflecting and thinking process by an individual or a group with regards to the problem.
- e) **Philosophical Conclusion:** A conclusion is philosophical only when it is reached by philosophers, i.e. with a person or a group of persons who have thought over the problem critically, methodically and rationally and only then have arrived at the conclusion. Here the conclusion was not philosophical as proper philosophical methods were not used.
- f) **Philosophical Effect:** These are the consequences of philosophical activity. The effects are never limited to a single person but affect the entire group. In this case the effect would have been entirely different. The forest created would have been a multi-specie forest which would have closely resembled the original one, it was trying to replicate. The effect on the flora and fauna would have been completely different and thus the ecology as a whole would have been affected positively.

4.1) Dilemma, and its Resolution: The Agencies involved in this original issue were obviously faced with a dilemma, they had to act fast (probably under the government pressure), they had no prior experience of afforestation of such a magnitude, they had no data about the ecosystem which had existed in the region before, they decided to go for a solution without proper planning or understanding its long term effect. The solution would have been ‘taking the dilemma by its horns’, as such provide an alternative, viz. go for pilot project, ask for more time and do proper study of the historical ecosystem of the region and find out the trees and plants which were found in the region. Make a list of the flora and the ratio of their presence depending on the area, and then go for afforestation.

5) **Conclusion:** As seen above, I have used very basics of logic and philosophy to explain how philosophy would have contributed to the resolution of the problem, by preventing its happening in the first place. There are also other methods we can use including inductive and deductive methods, testing the validity and soundness of the arguments, finding and pointing out the fallacy in the proposed solution. However, I will not elaborate these due to constraint of space.

However as we see, the application of philosophical logic in the case of environment sustenance and regeneration is enormous. We can use logic in preventing and solving many ecological crises around the world and thus, contribute to caring for our common home, the earth.

6) **References:**

1. NELFED Presentation by MPSM, Nashik.
2. Paradigms of Forest Conservation by C. Elliot.
3. Inductive and Deductive reasoning by Dr. Shalini, Asst. Prof. of Philosophy, S.N. Sinha College, Jehanabad.
4. Forest biodiversity in a changing climate: which logic for conservation strategies? By Harald Schaich and Mirjam Milad.

Presented By:

Savio Saldanha SJ

savio.saldanhasj@gmail.com